

Authoring Tools Descriptive Framework guidelines: rules and conditions

(Appendix)

References:

AT: Authoring Tool
EUO: End-User Output
AS: Authoring System
CMS: Content Management System

Key Properties:

Flexibility (AS)
Usability (AS)
Availability (AS)
Depth (EUO)
User Involvement (EUO)
Technological Enhancement (EUO)
Software Structure (EUO)

Flexibility

Key Property of: Authoring System

Summary: It describes the tool's ability to adapt to different purposes, authors' needs, and workflows.

Sub properties: Configurability, Modularity, Interoperability, Multi-Platform integration, Content and interaction Variability, Reusability.

Guidelines:

Sub property	Rules and conditions
Configurability The ability of a system to be adjusted or customized using predefined settings or parameters without modifying its core structure.	- It increases proportionally to: <ul style="list-style-type: none">- available DataTypes, since they are also easily integrated in the EUO by Visualization and Perceived Quality components;- The possibility to create new DataTypes, according to a balanced Authoring Complexity.
Modularity The degree to which a system is built from independent, interchangeable components (modules) that can be added, removed, or replaced without affecting the entire system.	- It becomes a predominant aspect if Software Distribution is Integrated. - It increases according with: <ul style="list-style-type: none">- The number of built-in modules;- The possible combinations among built-in modules;- The number of available addons/plugins;- The increment of the authoring power through the plugins, empowering DataTypes, Immersivity, and IoT connectivity.
Interoperability	- It increases: <ul style="list-style-type: none">- if Ownership

<p>The possibility of integration with external systems and APIs, import/export data-formats and storage management</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - includes ready-to-use APIs, - Includes Opensource Licence Model; - proportional to the number and sophistication* of importable /exportable DataTypes. <p>-It decreases as DataTypes relies on proprietary formats.</p> <p>Notes: * Domain specifics formats, utilities and meta-formats.</p>
<p>Multi-Platform Integration*</p> <p>The ability of a tool to run and deploy on different devices, operating systems, or VR/AR setups.</p> <p>* It refers to both AS and EUO.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - It increases if Software Distribution includes cross-platform deployment and distribution strategies. - It increases proportionally to available Immersivity modalities; - It increases proportionally to AS' Visualization and Interaction possibilities.
<p>Content and interaction Variability</p> <p>The ability to support different types of content, interaction logic, or user experiences.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - It increases as much as Authoring Complexity allows inspection, animation and user's interactions with properties of available entities; - It is proportional to the number of available Interaction Mechanics modalities, especially if creation of new mechanisms is possible and co-exists with creation of new DataTypes.
<p>Reusability</p> <p>The ability to reuse configurations, templates, or assets across different projects.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - It increases if Software Distribution relies on consistent CMS*; - It increases if Authoring Complexity allows decoupling entities/functionalities from singular projects**. <p>Notes: * Referred to the common meaning of assets' reusability. ** Referred to the configuration of custom behaviours/entities and streamlined workflows to share them across different EUOs.</p>

Usability

Key Property of: Authoring System

Summary: It describes how easily and efficiently authors can learn, navigate and operate through the AT's functionalities.

Sub-properties: Learnability, Efficiency, Memorability, Accessibility.

Guidelines:

Sub property	Rules and conditions
<p>Learnability</p> <p>How quickly authors explore and comprehend the system.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - It usually decreases with high levels of Authoring Complexity (higher learning curve); - It increases: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - when Authoring Complexity guarantee authoring process consistency; - if User's role includes Flow Customization (expertise-based interfaces); - if AS' Perceived Quality includes well-designed UI, which improves comprehension; - When Ownership includes community support, documentations and example projects.
<p>Efficiency</p> <p>How quickly authors can complete</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - It increases according to: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Authoring Complexity: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - If it provides multi-mode authoring processes;

tasks, minimizing effort and maximizing productivity.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - If it provides reusable entities/templates; - If it provides debugging and test features; - User's role: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - If it includes multi-user collaboration, improving co-authoring; - If it includes Flow Customization; - Interaction Mechanics: if error tolerance is provided; - Ownership: if open projects and assets are provided; - Perceived Quality: if it includes optimization tools.
Memorability How easily authors can recall how to use the tool after a period of inactivity.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - It usually decreases with Authoring Complexity (higher variety of components). On high levels of Authoring Complexity, documentation's relevance increases; - It increases if User's role includes Flow Customization (providing isolation of authoring tasks);
Accessibility How inclusive the tool is for diverse authors, considering support for assistive technologies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - It increases if <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Interaction Mechanics integrates adaptive UI options and UX alternatives (contrast, fonts, assistant integration); - If Interaction (Input Hardware) includes hardware alternatives; - If Software distribution provides suitable solutions for platform-support.

Availability

Key Property of: Authoring System

Summary: it describes how licensing, technical requirements and market adoption's level impact on the overall sustainability of the tool.

Sub-properties: Platform Independence, Setup simplicity, Licensing suitability, Ecosystem Maturity.

Guidelines:

Sub property	Rules and conditions
Platform independence* How accessible the tool is across platforms and OS and web access. * It refers to AS.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - It mainly increases if Software Distribution includes Web-based or cross-platform solutions. - It increases if Software Distribution includes online/offline tool's capabilities.
Setup simplicity How easy it is to install, configure, and start using the tool.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - It decreases proportionally if one or more possibilities among Immersivity, Interaction, Visualization, IoT Connectivity are strongly considered (due to hardware / software dependencies); -It increases if Ownership includes suitable tutorials for the setup.
Licensing suitability The flexibility of the licensing model, including costs, restrictions, open-source availability, self-host	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - It increases considerably as much as Ownership includes open source licence or free licence; - Alternatively, it decreases with software's price and features' limitations.

options and integration with external systems.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - It increases if Software distribution promotes self-hostable solutions. - It decreases if policies are not aligned with institutional or academic ones.
<p>Ecosystem maturity</p> <p>The overall level of tool's adoption, considering long-term support, community user base and documentation quality.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - It increases proportionally to Ownership, considering: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - authors community size; - assets, documentation and projects available; - relevance and number of uses cases; - long-term support;

Depth

Key Property of: End-User Output

Summary: It describes the richness, complexity, and structural sophistication of the content and experiences generable by the tool.

Sub-properties: Information density, Narrative dynamicity, Quality of discovery.

Guidelines:

Sub property	Rules and conditions
<p>Information density</p> <p>How rich, structured, and complex the experience is in terms of content, narrative, and system depth.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - It mainly increases with Structural/Narrative granularity (as more granular narratives implies deeper storytelling), and educational activities (Purpose); - It increases proportionally to DataTypes if they are active parts in the EUO;
<p>Narrative dynamicity</p> <p>Defines the ability to innovative storytelling experiences, influenced by the tool's support for logic-based progression and procedural elements.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - It increases proportionally to Structure/Narrative granularity, especially if it includes non-linear stories, generative or procedural contents. - It increases as Interaction Mechanics includes various interactions, empowering dynamicity in the overall experience; - It increases proportionally to available options in Interactions and Visualizations (hardware); -It increases with the number and sophistication of Purpose's available modalities for learning objectives.
<p>Quality of discovery</p> <p>How experience balances user's discovery activity, details of contents, sophistication of interactions.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - It increases homogeneously if <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Perceived Quality includes: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - High levels of visual representations, - Nudges, - Optimized engineering; - AND Interaction mechanics includes suitable interactions, accessible and adaptive UI; - It increases with integration of learning objective (included in Purposes), especially if User'role includes multi-user activities. - Additionally, it increases if Immersivity and/or IoT Connectivity include available possibilities.

User Involvement

Key Property of: End-User Output

Summary: It describes the end-user’s capability to interact, participate, and actively influence the experience.

Sub-properties: Level of control, Embodiment, Session consistency, Collaboration, Task complexity.

Guidelines:

Sub property	Rules and conditions
<p>Level of control</p> <p>How users can influence or change the sequentiality of the experience.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - It increases proportionally to User’s role involvement level; - It increases if Granularity/narrative structure includes non-linear narratives (providing dynamic EUO); - It increases if User’s role includes personalising the experience’s settings (es. altering Task complexity).
<p>Embodiment</p> <p>how deeply users feel integrated into the experience, influenced by immersive elements, emotional components and spatial interaction mechanics</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - It increases if Immersivity has relevance in EUO, especially if: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Interactions Hardware includes haptics or physical sensors, - Interaction Mechanics include physical and self-reflective interactions; - It increases if User’s role: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Includes flow customization (it improves experience’s personalization), - and/or it includes multi-user activities; - It increases proportionally to Perceived Quality (referring to emotional and cognitive experience’s settings).
<p>Session consistency</p> <p>How user progress and personalizations are persistent, ensuring continuity into the experience across multiple sessions.</p>	<p>Its relevance directly relies on <i>persistency</i>: it increases if Software distribution includes user-data management features, furthermore:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - It increases with <i>replayability</i>: allowing to collect advancements, save and restore sessions; - It increases if User’s role includes editable settings preferences in the experience, providing persistent <i>personalization</i>.
<p>Collaboration</p> <p>How experience can support multi-user interactions and real-time collaboration.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Its relevance directly relies on User’s role including multi-user features; - It increases if Immersivity includes virtuality, as co-presence is provided; - It increases if Structural/Narrative Granularity includes high levels of dynamicity affected to multi-user activities.
<p>Task complexity</p> <p>Level of complexity of the users’ activities and their impact on rewarding and experience’s manipulation.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - It increases according to <i>IDN dynamicity</i>, depending on a balanced levels of: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Structural/Narrative Granularity’s depth level; - complexity of available User’s role strategies; - Interaction Mechanics’s sophistication of solutions and metaphors; - Relevance of educational activities in Purpose.

Technological Enhancement

Key Property of: End-User Output

Summary: It describes the integration of advanced technological elements to improve the end-user experience.

Sub-properties: Virtuality continuity, Aesthetic adaptation, Analytics integration.

Guidelines:

Sub property	Rules and conditions
<p>Virtuality continuity</p> <p>Describes the possibility to configure different immersion modalities for the EUO, allowing transitions between AR, MR, VR, and physical interaction modes across the Virtuality-Reality Continuum.</p>	<p>- Its relevance directly relies on Immersivity, and the number of available possibilities, especially:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - If Interaction mechanics includes consistency among tools across different modalities; - If Authoring Complexity includes continuity across virtual modalities; - If IoT Connectivity or Interaction/Visualization include suitable solutions for each modality. <p>- Furthermore, it increases if Software Distribution includes cross-platform and Interactions Mechanics includes multi-platform activities.</p>
<p>Aesthetic adaptation</p> <p>It describes the ability of the tool to support a wide range of artistic and design choices (from photo realism to stylized), enabling complex interactions, performance optimizations, and visual adaptability to different projects.</p>	<p>- It increases proportionally to Perceived Quality possibilities (referring to graphical settings and real-time interactions and simulations);</p> <p>-It increases if Perceived Quality includes performance optimization techniques;</p> <p>- It increases proportionally to balanced sophistication of Visualization, Interactions Hardware and Interaction Mechanism solutions.</p>
<p>Analytics integration</p> <p>It describes how the tool integrates features to track user interactions, and collect data , also based on real-time analysis.</p>	<p>- It becomes relevant if Software Distribution includes user-data management with Analytics features, especially when Purpose includes high levels of learning programs (training, tests, evaluation).</p> <p>-It increases if Authoring Complexity includes features for authors to plan analytics sessions with the end-users' experience.</p> <p>- Alternatively, it increases if Ownership includes flexible APIs and interoperability possibilities (allowing to integrate external tracking services).</p>

Software Structure

Key Property of: End-User Output

Summary: It describes how the AT's software design ensures efficient execution, content management, and long-term stability.

Sub-properties: Execution simplicity, Content Management Efficacy, Solidity.

Guidelines:

Sub property	Rules and conditions
<p>Execution simplicity</p> <p>Describes how simple the tool's deployment and execution processes are, including the presence of automatic workflows or built-in front-end applications.</p>	<p>- It generally increases if Software Distribution:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - includes simplified pipelines for the available deployment strategies, - includes deployment strategies promoting built-in front-end solutions (e.g ready-to-use web-viewer or platform-specific apps); <p>- It generally decreases with a relevant role of IoT Connectivity, Visualization or Interaction hardware components, if complex solutions are contemplated in EUO (e.g. phygital setups).</p>

<p>Content Management Efficacy</p> <p>Describes how easily authors can update content and modify experience's logic.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Its relevance directly depends on Software Distribution if it includes updatability. - It increases with balanced proportion considering: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Variety and complexity of DataTypes streamed between AS and EUO, - Authoring Complexity level needed to manage data.
<p>Solidity (scalability, security, stability)</p> <p>It describes the system's stability, security, and scalability.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - It depends on <i>stability</i>, which improves with the maturity of the technological stack and frameworks included in Software Distribution, and reported as Ecosystem Maturity. - <i>Stability</i> may be affected when IoT Connectivity, Interaction, and Visualization hardware components operate simultaneously in the EUO, especially if maintenance is not properly planned. - Solidity may be affected by <i>security</i> requirements, which must be ensured through Software Distribution by supporting (at minimum) encryption, authentication and access control. Alternatively, <i>security</i> can rely on external or self-hosted solutions, if permitted by Ownership policies. - Solidity relies on <i>scalability</i>, which increases if Software Distribution includes scalable technology in order to guarantee (and then proportionally to): <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - multi-user features (included in User's Role), - Interoperability with IoT Connectivity, - High levels of Perceived Quality, - Performance adaptability, ensuring good quality of the EUO across different devices (reported as Multi-Platform Integration).